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Research Article

Development and Validation of HPLC Method for Determination of an API in Presence of its Degradation Products

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ABSTRACT

The present study describes the development and validation of HPLC (HILIC) method for determination of an Imeglimin in presence of its degradation products. The proposed HPLC method utilizes a new HILIC for the determination of Imeglimin. The separation was achieved by using ZIC-HILIC (5 μ m; 150 x 4.6 mm ID.column by using solvent A; 15mM ammonium acetate solvent B; acetonitrile (50:50, v/v) as mobile phase with the flow rate of 1ml/min. Where detection was carried out by UV detector (SPD-10AVP) at 230nm. The retention time was found to be 5.138min. The described method was linear over the range of 1.56 –50 μ g/ml. 1.56 –50 μ g/ml . The mean regression equation was found to be $y = 336299x + 344398$, $R^2 = 0.9997$. The precision, ruggedness, accuracy, repeatability, robustness values were also within the prescribed limits. Imeglimin was exposed to acidic, basic, oxidative, thermal, photo degradation and stressed samples were analysed by the proposed method. Chromatographic peak purity results indicated the absence of co-eluting peaks with the main peak of Imeglimin, which demonstrated the specificity of method for estimation of Imeglimin in presence of degradation products. The proposed method can be used for routine analysis of Imeglimin.

INTRODUCTION

Imeglimin is a novel oral medication used to treat type 2 diabetes (T2D). It's the first in a new class of antidiabetic drugs called glimins, which contain tetrahydrotriazine. Imeglimin's mechanism of action is distinct from older antidiabetic drugs, and it's expected to be used in combination with diet

and exercise or as an add on therapy. Imeglimin's effects include: Enhanced insulin secretion imeglimin increases insulin secretion and protects beta-cell function. the mode of action of Imeglimin is unique and distinct compared with other major classes of therapeutic agents. It involves dual effects, both to enhance insulin action and to

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reverse pancreatic β -cell dysfunction. Imeglimin primarily works by improving glucose-stimulated insulin secretion (GSIS) and enhancing insulin action, ultimately improving glucose homeostasis. It achieves this by increasing nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD⁺) in pancreatic beta cells, which in turn leads to enhanced insulin release and improved mitochondrial function. Imeglimin also helps preserve beta cell mass and potentially reduces hepatic glucose output.[1,2,3] Stability testing forms an important part of the process of drug product development. The purpose of stability testing is to provide evidence on how the quality of a drug substance varies with time under the influence of a variety of environmental factors such as temperature, humidity and light and enables recommendation of storage conditions, retest periods, and shelf life to be established. The assay of Imeglimin API (Active pharmaceutical Ingredient) in stability test sample needs to be determined using stability indicating method, as recommended by the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines and USP. [4,5,6] The present work was designed to develop a simple, precise and rapid analytical LC procedure, which would serve as method for analysis of Imeglimin API in presence of its degradation products. In this method isocratic elution method is selected for the analysis of Imeglimin API because it gave better base line separation and peak width, which is suitable for the routine analysis of Imeglimin. Hydrophilic Interaction Liquid Chromatography (HILIC) is a liquid chromatography technique used for separating polar compounds, particularly those that are difficult to separate using reversed-phase chromatography. It utilizes a polar stationary phase and a mobile phase with a high organic solvent content, typically acetonitrile. The separation mechanism relies on the preferential interaction of polar compounds with the hydrophilic stationary phase in the presence of a

highly organic mobile phase. In view of above in the present study we hereby report the development and Validation of HPLC method for determination of Imeglimin API in presence of its degradation products as per ICH guidelines. In order to establish the stability indicating nature of the method, forced degradation of Imeglimin was performed under various stress conditions (basic, acidic oxidative, thermal and photo) and stressed samples were analyzed by the proposed method. The proposed LC method was able to separate the drug from degradation products generated during forced degradation studies. The developed method was validated as per ICH guidelines and its updated international convention. The linearity of response, precision, repeatability, accuracy, robustness, ruggedness, specificity, LOD, LOQ of the described method has been checked.[7,8,9,10]

Experimental Conditions

Reagents and reference samples

The API of Imeglimin was purchased from Yarrow Chemicals Ltd. Ammonium acetate was purchased from Merck Ltd. (Mumbai-India) HPLC grade acetonitrile, methanol and HPLC grade water were purchased from Merck (Mumbai, India). 0.20 μ and 0.45 μ nylon membrane filters were used and purchased from UltraChrom Innovatives Pvt. Ltd. (India). All other chemicals and reagents were used of HPLC grade.

Instrumentation

The high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) of Shimadzu SCL-10AVP inbuilt with binary pump (LC-10ATVP), UV detector (SPD-10AVP), Rheodyne 20 μ l loop capacity manual injector (P/N 77251) was used throughout the analysis. The LC-Solution software was used to interpret the HPLC reports. ZIC-HILIC (5 μ m; 150

x 4.6 mm ID.) column was purchased from UltraChrom Innovatives (P) Ltd. (India) was used throughout the analysis. Digital weighing balance (ME-204) purchased from Mettler-Toledo (USA), ultra-sonicator Labman® purchased from UltraChrom Ltd, India. Digital pH meter from Mettler-Toledo was purchased from (Mumbai-India). 50 µl micro-syringe was purchased from Hamilton USA. 0.20µ and 0.45µ nylon membrane filters were purchased from Phenomenex® Mumbai, India.

The Standard and sample solutions were prepared separately by dissolving standard and sample in a solvent mixture of Acetonitrile:Methanol:Water (20:60:20 v/v).

Optimization of Chromatographic Conditions

The chromatographic conditions were optimized by different means. (Using different column, different buffer and different modes of HPLC run, Table 1, Fig. a-d.

Standard and Sample Preparation

Table no 1. Method Development For HPLC Analysis of Imeglimin API

Trials	Coloumn used	Mobile Phase	Mobile Phase composition	Flow Rate mL/Min	Observation	Result
1	Zodiac C8 5µ, (150 X 4.6 mm. ID.)	15mM Ammonium acetate-Acetonitrile;	50:50 v/v	1 ml/min	Tailing Factor Was Somewhat High	Method Rejected
2	Zodiac C8 5µ, (150 X 4.6 mm. ID.)	15mM Ammonium acetate-Acetonitrile	Gradient	1 ml/min	Baseline Was Not Stable	Method Rejected
3	Zodiac C8 5µ, (150 X 4.6 mm. ID.)	15mM Ammonium acetate-Acetonitrile	60:40 v/v	1 ml/min	Somewhat Higher Tailing Factor	Method Rejected
4	Zic-HILIC (150 X 4.6 mm. ID.)	15mM Ammonium acetate - Acetonitrile;	50:50 v/v	1 ml/min	Imeglimin Separated As Per The ICH Guidelines.	Method Accepted

Validation

For repeatability the freshly prepared solution of Imeglimin was injected 6 times to determine the closeness of results achieved for relative standard deviation (RSD) and data is presented in table no 2. To establish the intra-day and inter-day precision of the method, Imeglimin was analysed on one day and three separate days. Intra day and Inter day precision were calculated and the data are presented in Table no 3.

Robustness of the method was investigated by varying the chromatographic conditions such as changes of flow, changes in mobile phases. changes in wavelength. Robustness of the developed method was indicated by the overall SD between the data at each variable condition and presented in table no 4. Linearity was determined by injecting different concentration of sample solutions (50, 25, 12.5, 6.25, 3.12 and 1.56 ppm) and data is represented in table no 5.

Accuracy of marketed formulation was determined at 80%, 100%, 120% data is

represented in table no 6. Specificity of the proposed method was performed by analysing degraded sample solution of Imeglimin. Ruggedness was performed by different analyst. LOD/ LOQ was determined from linearity study. For system suitability freshly prepared solution of Imeglimin was injected 6 times to determine the closeness of results achieved for relative standard deviation (RSD) in percentage.

Forced Degradation Studies

Imeglimin was allowed to Hydrolyse in different strengths of acid (0.1M HCL), base (0.1M NaOH), hydrogen peroxide (3-6% H₂O₂). Imeglimin was also studied for its thermal degradation for 24hrs at 45 degree celcius and photo degradation for six hrs. An accurately weighed 5mg of Imeglimin API was dissolved in 5ml of Acetonitrile:Methanol:Water (20:60:20 v/v) to get 1000 ppm. Pipette out 0.2ml of 1000ppm and dilute it with 3.8 ml of

Acetonitrile:Methanol:Water (20:60:20 v/v) to make it 50ppm and samples for forced degradation is prepared. data is presented in table no 8.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chromatographic conditions: To develop a precise, linearity, specific and suitable stability indicating HPLC (HILIC-Hydrophilic Interaction Liquid Chromatography) method for analysis of Imeglimin, different chromatographic conditions were applied and the results observed are presented in Table 1 and and Figs. 1a-d. In case of HPLC various columns are available, but here Zic-HILIC (150 X 4.6 mm. ID.) column preferred because using this column peak shape, resolution and absorbance were good and Mobile Phase: 15mM Ammonium acetate - Acetonitrile; 50:50 v/v was selected.

Fig a: Trial 1

Fig b: Trial 2

Fig c: Trial 3

Fig d: Trial 4

Repeatability:

calculated RSDs for tested imeglimin was less than 2% which is quite significant in accordance with the ICH guidelines.

Table no 2 : Repeatability Study of Imeglimin

Sr. No.	Drug Name: Imeglimin
	Peak Area; Conc. 50 ppm
1	15516675
2	15000945
3	15017463
4	15013506
5	15286753
6	15004023
Mean	15139894
STD. DEV.	215528.4285
RSD (%)	1.42

Fig 1: Repeatability

Fig 2: Intraday Study

Fig 3: Interday study

Fig 4: Robustness Study:Flow Rate 1.1 ml/min

Fig 5: Robustness Study: Flow Rate 0.9 ml/min

Fig 6: Robustness Study: 52 %

Fig 7: Robustness Study: 48 %

Fig 8: Robustness Study: 232 nm

Fig 9: Robustness Study: 228 nm

Fig 10 : Calibration Curve of Imeglimin

Fig 11: Drug Accuracy Study:80%

Fig 12: Drug Accuracy Study:100%

Fig 13: drug accuracy:120%

Fig 14: Chromatogram of Ruggedness

Fig 15: Stability Studies: Effect Of 0.1N NaoH

Table no 3: Intraday Precision Data of Imeglimin

Drug Name: imeglimin					
S. No.	Concentration (ppm)	Area	Average	Std. Deviation	%RSD
1	50 ppm	15516675	15178361	293104.90	1.93
	50 ppm	15000945			
	50 ppm	15017463			
2	50 ppm	15013506	15101427	160566.76	1.06

3	50 ppm	15286753	15887359	97457.27	0.61
	50 ppm	15004023			
	50 ppm	15845420			
	50 ppm	15998765			
	50 ppm	15817892			
Range of % RSD					0.61-1.93

Table 3: Interday/Intermediate Precision Data of Imeglimin

Drug Name: Imeglimin					
S. No.	Concentration (ppm)	Area	Average	Std. Deviation	%RSD
DAY 1	50 ppm	15845420	15887359	97457.27	0.61
	50 ppm	15998765			
	50 ppm	15817892			
DAY 2	50 ppm	17192518	17072818	103833.14	0.61
	50 ppm	17018911			
	50 ppm	17007026			
DAY 3	50 ppm	17113541	17151038	39957.45	0.23
	50 ppm	17146503			
	50 ppm	17193069			
Range of % RSD					0.23-0.61

Table no 4: Robustness data of Imeglimin

Variables	Imeglimin			
	t _R (min)	k'	T _f	N
Flow rate (+0.1 mL/min)	5.55	2.89	1.62	2728
Flow rate (-0.1 mL/min)	6.8	1.86	1.68	2820
Solvent B (+2%)	6.21	2.98	1.62	2936
Solvent B (-2%)	6.09	1.83	1.66	2660
Wavelength (+2°C)	6.12	1.85	1.65	2728
Wavelength (-2°C)	6.12	1.85	1.64	2750
Mean ± S.D.	6.15±0.40	2.21±0.56	1.65±0.02	

Table no 5: Linearity Data of Imeglimin

Name of Drug; Imeglimin		
S. No.	Concentration (µg/mL)	Area
1	1.56	699761
2	3.12	1423538
3	6.25	2566006
4	12.5	4543233
5	25	8826383
6	50	17111914
Regression Equation		y= 336299x + 344398

Correlation coefficient (R²)	0.9997
Std. error of intercept	64772.13715
Std. Dev. Of intercept	158658.6856
LOQ	4.72 µg/mL
LOD	1.42 µg/mL

Table no 6: Drug Accuracy Study; Imeglimin

Drug Name: Imeglimin			Drug content: 500 mg		Marketed formulation: Imeglyn-500 Tablet		
Std. conc. (%)	Std. (ppm)	Peak area	Drug (%)	Drug (ppm)	Peak area	Avg. peak area	Drug Rec. (%)
100%	50 ppm	15139894	80	39.90	12005621	12169964	101.16
				40	12106631		
				40.10	12397641		
			100	49.90	15075129	15243899	101.03
				50	15139894		
				50.10	15516675		
			120	59.90	18069283	18114990	99.73
				60	18107378		
				60.10	18168311		
Drug recovery Range (%) as per ICH = 100±10%						99.73 % - 101.16 %	

Precision: The results obtained in intraday precision studies was found within 0.61-1.93 %, peak are found with %RSD NMT 2% which was in agreement with system suitability. this confirms that the method was precise. The results obtained in interday precision studies was found within 0.23-0.61%, peak are found with %RSD NMT 2% which was in agreement with system suitability. this confirms that the method was precise.

Robustness: Overall %RSD of results with change in flow, wavelength and mobile phase composition observed within acceptance criteria, method is robust in terms of slight change in internal method parameters, hence Robustness is justified.

Linearity: Correlation coefficient observed within acceptance criteria hence method is linear, and linearity is justified.

Accuracy: % Mean recovery of Imeglimin observed within acceptance criteria 99.73%-101.16%, also % RSD of recovery observed within acceptance criteria; hence accuracy is justified.

Specificity: This result indicates that the peak of the analyte was pure and it confirmed the specificity of the method.

Ruggedness: By comparing with the optimized chromatogram, the method indicated that by performing with different analyst method was found stable.

LOD/LOQ: They were found to be LOD 1.42 µg/mL and LOQ 4.72 µg/mL

System Suitability Testing:

Table no 7: System suitability of Imeglimin

Test Criteria	Results	Acceptance criteria
Theoretical plates (<i>N</i>)	2864	≥ 2000
Capacity Factor (<i>K'</i>)	1.42	≤ 0.5
Tailing factor (<i>T</i>)	1.403	< 1.5
Retention time (<i>t_R</i>)	5.13 min.	> <i>k'</i>
Wavelength (nm)	230 nm	> 200 nm

Repeatability (% RSD)	1.42	< 2%
Intra-Day Precision (% RSD)	0.61-1.93	< 2%
Inter-Day Precision (% RSD)	0.23-0.61	< 2%
Linearity range	1.56 –50 µg/ml	NA
Regression equation	y= 336299x + 344398	NA
Correlation Coefficient (r2)	0.9997	NA
SE of intercept (Se)	64772.13715	NA
SD of intercept (Sa)	158658.6856	NA
LOQ ^a (µg/mL)	4.72 µg/mL	NA
LOD ^a (µg/mL)	1.42 µg/mL	NA

All the parameters of system suitability are observed within specified limit. Hence system suitability is justified.

Forced Degradation Study:

Table no 8: Results of Stability Studies of Imeglimin

Drug Name: Imeglimin	t _R before degradation	t _R after degradation	No. of degradants	% degradation
Acid (0.1M HCl)	5.26	5.85	0 degradants	0.00%
Base (0.1M NaOH)	5.26	6.13	4 degradants	86.00%
Thermal (45°C)	5.26	6.003	0 degradants	0%
Oxidation (3-6% H ₂ O ₂)	5.26	6.338	0 degradation	0%
Sunlight exposed	5.26	6.109	0 degradation	0%

From above stability study, Imeglimin was found degraded in Base (0.1 M NaOH). 4 degradation products are obtained. Imeglimin was found stable in Acid (0.1 M HCl), Thermal (45°C), Oxidation (3-6% H₂O₂) Sunlight exposed.

CONCLUSION

The developed HILIC method was found to be linear over concentration range. Therefore, the developed HILIC method can be applied for routine quantitative and qualitative analysis of Imeglimin. The developed HILIC method was validated as per the ICH guidelines. The ICH guidelines that force degradation is designed to help to determine the intrinsic stability of the molecule by establishing degradation pathways in order to identify the likely degradation products and to validate the stability indicating power of the analytical procedures used. In this work a

validated stability indicating method was developed for analysis of Imeglimin by force degradation study. This demonstrates that the method is suitable for the determination of Imeglimin in formulation without any interference from the degradation product and is endorsed for routine use in quality control industry laboratories. The proposed method has been shown to be stability indicating in nature.

Future Scope

- Analytical method development can be conveniently used for Quality control and routine determination of the drug in pharmaceutical industry.
- A highly sensitive, reproducible, simple and accurate analytical technique can be validated for the estimation of pharmaceutical dosage form.

- Stability indicating HPLC method for estimation of Imeglimin can be developed.
- Developed HPLC SIM for acidic, basic, oxidative, thermal, photolytic degradation.

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